

LOGBOOK

For Educate in Rights through
Arts, Culture and Creativity

LOGBOOK

EducArts! seek to people identify and promote human rights and European common values through Arts and Culture in a creative way. This will be achieved by mean of developing narratives emerged from both collaboration among learners (Co-creation) and self-learning.

Through using this logbook, the learner will immerse him/herself in the storytelling proposed by the educator, being able to follow the indications that, in an entertaining and instructive way, this guideline offers him/her. This logbook will ask deep questions, observations, comments, and even games (where the player can assume different roles while learning about civics concepts). All of this makes the learning experience not only more efficient but also funny.

The expected result for the learner who take this guide is awareness of the basic terms of European citizenship and the learning development of key skills considered necessary for an effective democratic participation. This logbook has been developed in digital format, in response to environmental concerns. However, the paper format can be used if it facilitates the learner's learning. Likewise, this material is a general example of how learning can be approached, and the educator can adapt this model to attend to specific learning situations, suggesting specific questions that can replace those used here.

We hope you enjoy the EducArts experience!
[EducArts! Partnership]

1

Initial Activity

Do you really know what Human Rights are?

It is a common and important topic. Therefore, in this activity we will explore the different human rights based on our prior knowledge of the topic. The first question we want to ask you is: What do you know about human rights and which of them do you know? Fill in the clouds with everything you know about each of the rights, including as many as you can think of. Also, if you feel up to it, you can try to explain them in a short sentence - there are no wrong answers, we will learn more about them in depth later! Work individually or with others around you to write down and explain as many human rights as possible.

Great! Now we will check the results by correcting the activity. We want you to go to the following website next: <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>. Read the list individually or with your classmates to try to see how many human rights you have managed to include in your brainstorming.

Answer as a group:

Were they all correct? Did you expect a shorter list? Do you think there are any rights that should be more comprehensive? Do you think any of them is missing considering how much the world has changed since the Universal Declaration of Human Rights was drafted?

2

Objects around us

The following activity is about the human rights that exist all around us, and has the main objective of highlighting them and expressing what they mean to us individually through objects. To do so, we ask you to choose three fundamental human rights that you consider important. For each of the rights, you will have to find at least 6 objects that you think are representative of each of these rights and make a sculpture with them. They can be photographs, objects from your own home such as clothes or various materials, waste that you throw away regularly, things related to culture or technology... The possibilities are endless! Just try to make sure that the objects are representative of the rights. With this in mind, take three photographs and print them out. You can paste them in the spaces available for them below. You can give a name to each one and explain them on the side.

Creativity to the max!

Photo 1

Photo 2

Photo 3

3

Human rights in our life

For the following activity you need to interact with people around you.

☞ **Choose 5 people**, try to make sure that characteristics such as age, gender, sexual orientation, religion or political ideology vary between them, thus maximising diversity of opinion.

☞ After that, you will play the role of a journalist: interview each of these people to describe what their ideal world would be like. Explain that they will have to talk about sustainability, economy, family or social life, leisure time... If the answers are short, try to ask questions related to the main topic. Then make a list of the main ideas of each of the 5 people.

☞ Finally, try to notice similarities in the answers, and see if some of the main ideas are repeated in several interviews. Make a final list with all of them!

Participant 1

Participant 2

Participant 3

Participant 4

Participant 5

Our designed utopia

4

Drawings of the future

Continuing with ideal or dystopian future worlds, what we ask you to do next is to **draw pictures** on the left related to the ideal world you imagine. You can include words, objects, feelings, situations, people, animals, and even planets or cities! In contrast to this ideal world, on the right you will have to draw everything that harms this ideal world, problems that currently exist or some that you imagine may come true at some point. There are no limits!

Utopia

Dystopia

How do you think you can contribute to building the world you represent on the left?

How could institutions such as governments, schools or universities contribute?

5

Get out on the street!

External activity! To do this, we ask you to look for an activity in your neighbourhood, town, city or area in which human rights are valued. They can be art exhibitions, lectures, films, concerts, museums,... If your situation makes it impossible to attend any of these events in person, you can watch movies or listen to songs from home. Many museums even have online visits available on their websites where you can see the different paintings from the comfort of your own home! Ask the people you see around you, after finishing the activity, what they thought of it and what they think it has to do with human rights. Afterwards, explain in your own words:

What have you learnt in this activity?

How the activity relates to human rights?

What else would you have liked to know ?

You can glue the tickets or some pieces of the panflets in here

6

Different but equal

The following activity is very simple, but it **involves many people!**

Go to a crowded place, such as a bar, a subway or bus stop, the center or square of your city or neighbourhood. There, ask everyone you meet to write on the next page, in a sentence of 10 words or less, what human rights mean to them. They can express themselves freely and sign or draw whatever they want.

If you can, get from home or buy an ink pad. On a different page, ask if they would like to collaborate with their fingerprint to create a group circular drawing. You can make spirals, circles, drawings, or anything else you can think of with each other's fingerprints.

What are human rights for you?

6

Different but equal

Fingerprints mural

Your screens, your interfaces

For the next activity, **find 5 examples** online where Human Rights are violated or protected. You can find them on social networks such as *Instagram*, *Twitter*, *TikTok* or *Facebook* or perhaps in digital media such as online newspapers, websites or blogs. Display the opinions of others below, and answer for each of them the following questions:

- *What are the intentions of the author of the post?*
- *Do you fully agree with the author, and why?*
- *You might disagree with the publication, how would you respond to the author? If not, how would people contrary to that opinion respond?*